

NEWSLETTER

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Visit of Researchers from the Technical University of Sofia

SMARTNESS had the pleasure of welcoming Dr. Antoni Ivanov and Dr. Atanas Vlahov from the Technical University of Sofia (TU-Sofia, Bulgaria) during their visit to Brazil on October 27th, 2025, as part of ongoing collaborations with Brazilian universities.

[Read more](#)

ETSI Delegation Visit in Collaboration with ANATEL

SMARTNESS welcomed a delegation from the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), as part of a series of initiatives carried out in partnership with the Brazilian National Telecommunications Agency (ANATEL). The visit aimed to strengthen cooperation in research, innovation, and the development of telecommunications standards.

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Distinguished Lecture by Mischa Dohler and Visit to the 5G Studio

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We are delighted to announce that Dr. Mischa Dohler – VP Emerging Technologies at Ericsson in Silicon Valley and world-renowned expert in immersive internet, 6G and wireless communications – successfully delivered his acclaimed IEEE Distinguished Lecturer at FEEC/UNICAMP, entitled “The Dawn of an Immersive Internet: AR, AI & API on the Road to 6G”.

Presentation of Achievements at the UNICAMP Postdoc Meeting

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On September 10, 2025, UNICAMP hosted the Post-Docs Meeting on Research Management. This event was designed to spark dialogue, share experiences, and demonstrate the best research management practices. One of the event’s highlights was the Engineering Research Center SMARTNESS, which was recognized by UNICAMP’s Grant Office as a success story.

Recognition of Profs. Hugo Figueroa and Luiz Bittencourt Among the World's Most Influential Scientists

Professor Hugo E. H. Figueroa, Director of the School of Electrical and Computer Engineering (FEEC) at Unicamp and Partnerships Coordinator of SMARTNESS, and Professor Luiz F. Bittencourt, Education and Dissemination Coordinator of the project, have been included in the list of the world's most influential scientists.

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Participation and Contributions at SIGCOMM 2025

At SIGCOMM 2025, one of ACM's leading conferences on data communication, SMARTNESS participated with several researchers in the conference organization, as well as with multiple contributions in the poster and demo sessions. The group presented its latest studies on RAN disaggregation, SmartNIC-based emulation, digital twins, federated learning, drones network emulation, and cloud gaming.

[Read more](#)

Visit of FAPESP's New Innovation Managers for Strategic Dialogue

SMARTNESS welcomed Professors Liliam Carrete and Douglas Zampieri, FAPESP's new Technology, Partnerships and Innovation Managers, at UNICAMP. The visit included presentations on the center's strategic vision, achievements from the first two years, and future plans.

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Keynote Talks at IEEE COLCOM 2025

SMARTNESS professors participated as Keynote Speakers at IEEE COLCOM 2025 in Popayán, Colombia. Carlos Trujillo discussed the role of space for communications and computing in 5G and 6G networks, while Luiz Bittencourt addressed the computing continuum beyond cloud and edge. Their participation highlights the center's contribution to debates on the future of networks and computing.

[Read more](#)

Visit to Research Centers in Spain by Prof. Christian Rothenberg

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Prof. Christian Rothenberg, PI of SMARTNESS, visits leading research centers in Spain. His agenda in Madrid included IMDEA Networks Institute, Telefónica Innovación Digital, and Universidad Carlos III. In Barcelona, he also delivered talks at Telefónica and CTTC, presenting ongoing research at SMARTNESS, focusing on open-source tools for 5G/6G experimentation.

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